

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF “HEYDAR ALIYEV-100: BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCE BOOK” IN THE STUDY OF THE HERITAGE OF NATIONAL LEADER HEYDAR ALIYEV

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Abstract

Standing alongside the most influential politicians of his time, Heydar Aliyev played an exceptional role in promoting the modern face of Azerbaijan, the rich values of our people, and in gaining a worthy position in the system of international relations of our country. The resolution of the Armenia-Azerbaijan conflict on the basis of the norms and principles of international law was the main task set by the Great Leader, and all the resources of our country and the potential of our people were mobilized to restore historical justice. The strong Azerbaijani state, which is the masterpiece of the Great Leader, proved its ability to protect its sovereignty by winning a glorious Victory in the 44-day Patriotic War.

Information resources play an important role in studying the heritage of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev. One of such bibliographic resources is “Heydar Aliyev-100: Bibliographic reference book”. The bibliographic index fully reflects the genius, integrity of his personality, high intellectual level, deep scientific worldview, unwavering loyalty to the ideas of national statehood, and spiritual richness of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev. At the same time, this bibliographic publication once again proves that very few prominent statesmen in the world can be compared with the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev in terms of the number and volume of their scientific and theoretical works. It is in this respect that the National Leader Heydar Aliyev is a phenomenal personality, and the mentioned bibliographic reference book is the most vivid example of this fact. Being an indispensable source for a wide readership, the universal “Heydar Aliyev-100: Bibliographic Reference Book” plays an important role in providing information to our numerous intellectuals, especially the younger generation.

Keywords: The rich heritage of the Great Leader, Heydar Aliyev-100, bibliographic reference book, young generation, information provision.

Introduction

World-class political and statesman Great Leader Heydar Aliyev is one of the rare figures in the history of the Azerbaijani people, whose rich heritage is always in the center of attention of researchers. Thus, information resources dedicated to the heritage of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev play an important role.

A bibliographic reference book about the president, a leader, which has no analogues in the world, was first published 22 years ago, dedicated to the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Heydar Aliyev. By the decision of the Scientific Council of Baku State University, in 2003, for the first time in our country, a bibliographic reference book dedicated to the National Leader Heydar Aliyev from the series “Outstanding Statesmen of the World” was published. The universal bibliographic work is dedicated to the 80th anniversary of the outstanding statesman of the world, the founder of our national independence, Great Leader Heydar Alirza oglu Aliyev. The book contains a bibliographic description of the book in 544 titles. The compilers of the bibliographic index are Professor Abuzar Khalafov and Associate Professor Solmaz Sadiqova. The bibliographic reference book, published for the first time in Azerbaijan, is the first step taken in the field of bibliography of Heydar Aliyev's heritage and has 434 pages in Azerbaijani, 446 pages in Russian and 455 pages in English. The fact that the work, which is the fruit of a remarkable initiative and hard work, was published separately in Azerbaijani with a circulation of 5000,

Russian with a circulation of 3000 and English with a circulation of 2000 confirms both the scale of its scientific importance, its massness and the breadth of its readership. At the same time, it proves that the inexhaustible interest in the personality and heritage of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev is growing stronger.

Problem setting

By the Order of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, dated September 29, 2022, 2023 was declared the “Year of Heydar Aliyev” in the Republic of Azerbaijan. In accordance with the Action Plan of Baku State University for the Year of Heydar Aliyev, twenty years after the publication of the first bibliographic work[3;4;5], “Heydar Aliyev-100: Bibliographic Information Book” was re-prepared and published in 2024 by the decision of the Scientific Council of Baku State University. [6, p.8].

The author of the idea of the printed book consisting of 580 pages is the rector of Baku State University Elchin Babayev, the compiler is Doctor of Philosophy in History, Associate Professor Solmaz Sadiqova, the scientific editor is Doctor of Philosophy in Philology, Associate Professor Alamdar Bayramov, and the reviewer is the director of the National Library of Azerbaijan, Professor Karim Tahirov

The main part

In such a fundamental bibliographic index covering the years 1923-2023, the materials are presented in chronological order. “Heydar Aliyev-100: Bibliographic information book” consists of four parts and

eight subsections. The provision of information about the orders and medals, honorary titles, awards received by the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev during the Soviet period, and the dissertations written about him from 2002 to 2023 indicates the richness of the information capacity of the bibliographic resource.

The provision of 46 books of the multi-volume "Our Independence is Eternal" with a volume of 23062 pages or 1441.3 printed sheets under one source (source 157) serves to provide information by revealing the content of each book of the collection [6, p.195].

Aliyev, H. Our Independence is Eternal: In 46 books: Speeches, speeches, statements, letters, interviews [Text]. - Baku: Azernashr, 1997 - 2013.

- V.1. June, 1993 - May, 1994. - 1997. - 612 p.
 V.2. May, 1994 - December, 1994.- 1997.- 604 p.
 V.3. December, 1994 - June, 1995.- 1997. - 488 p.
 V.4. June, 1995 - November, 1995. - 1997. - 528p.
 V.5. November, 1995 - March, 1996. - 1998. - 500p.
 V.6. March, 1996 - June, 1996. - 1998. - 512 p.
 V.7. June, 1996 - November, 1996.- 1998. -520 p.
 V.8. November, 1996 - March, 1997. - 1998. - 488p.
 V.9. March, 1997 - May, 1997. - 2000. - 466 p.
 V.10. May, 1997 - July, 1997.- 2002.- 472 p.
 V.11. July, 1997 - August, 1997.- 2003.- 452 p.
 V. 12. August, 1997 - October, 1997.- 2004.- 432p.
 V.13. October, 1997 - December, 1997. - 2004. - 520 p.
 V.14. December, 1997 - February, 1998. - 2005. - 520 p.
 V.15. March, 1998 - June, 1998. - 2005. - 528 p.
 V.16. June, 1998 - July, 1998. - 2005. - 552 p.
 V.17. July, 1998 - October, 1998. - 2006. - 528 p.
 V.18. October, 1998 - December, 1998. - 2006. - 552 p.
 V.19. January, 1999 - April, 1999. - 2006. - 528p.
 V.20. April, 1999 - July, 1999. - 2007. - 536 p.
 V.21. July, 1999 - September, 1999. - 2007. - 480p.
 V.22. September, 1999 - November, 1999. - 2007. - 528 p.
 V.23. November, 1999 - December, 1999. - 2008. - 480 p.
 V.24. December, 1999 - February, 2000. - 2008. - 504 p.
 V.25. February, 2000 - March, 2000. - 2008. - 520p.
 V.26. March, 2000 - April, 2000. - 2009. - 512 p.
 V.27. April, 2000 - June, 2000. - 2009. - 496 p.
 V.28. June, 2000 - July, 2000. - 2009. - 480 p.
 V.29. July, 2000 - September, 2000. - 2009. - 480p.
 V.30. September, 2000 - November, 2000. - 2010. - 520 p.
 V.31. November, 2000 - January, 2001. - 2010. - 512 p.
 V.32. January, 2001 - March, 2001. - 2010. - 512p.
 V.33. March, 2001 - April, 2001. - 2011. - 480 p.
 V.34. May, 2001 - June, 2001. - 2011. - 488 p.
 V.35. June, 2001 - August, 2001. - 2011. - 520 p.

V.36. September, 2001 - November, 2001. - 2011. - 512 p.

V.37. November, 2001 - March, 2002. - 2011. - 520 p.

V.38. March, 2002 – May, 2002. – 2011. – 480 p.

V.39. June, 2002 - July, 2002. - 2012. - 480 p.

V.40. July, 2002 - September, 2002. - 2012. - 512p.

V.41. September, 2002 - October, 2002. - 2012. - 488 p.

V.42. October, 2002 - November, 2002. - 2012. - 472 p.

V.43. November, 2002 - February, 2003. - 2013. - 464 p.

V.44. February, 2003 – May, 2003. – 2013. – 376p.

V.45. May, 2003 – December, 2003. – 2013. – 384p.

V.46. Notes. – 2013. – 496 p.

The opening of the contents of the multi-volume can be considered an innovation of the author in this field. As an example, if we look at the opening of the contents of one book, we will see that it is possible to obtain all the information from June 1993 to May 1994. During the monitoring of one volume of the multi-volume, it became clear that in only one book, information can be obtained about up to 130 speeches, meetings, etc. of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev on various topics. For example, Our Independence is Eternal: Vol. I. June, 1993 - May, 1994: Speeches: speeches, statements, letters, interviews [Text] / Heydar Aliyev; ed. eg.: R. Mehdiyev, H. Orujov. - Baku: Azernashr, 1997. - 612 p.

Contents of the book:

Speech at the session of the Milli Majlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan (June 15, 1993);

Statement by Heydar Aliyev, Chairman of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Azerbaijan, acting as President of the Republic of Azerbaijan (July 2, 1993);

To His Excellency Bill Clinton, President of the United States of America (July 2, 1993);

To the participants of the 2nd meeting of the Economic Cooperation Organization in Istanbul (July 5, 1993);

Statement by Heydar Aliyev, Chairman of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Azerbaijan, acting as President of the Republic of Azerbaijan (July 5, 1993);

Interview with the Ostankino Interstate Television Company (July 6, 1993);

To His Excellency François Mitterrand, President of the French Republic (July 13, 1993);

Statement by Heydar Aliyev, Chairman of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Azerbaijan, acting as President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, and Mario Raffaelli, Chairman of the OSCE Minsk Conference on Nagorno-Karabakh, at a joint press conference (July 14, 1993);

To His Excellency Mohammed Hosni Mubarak, President of the Arab Republic of Egypt (July 21, 1993);

To the Chairman of the UN Security Council. Copy: UN Secretary-General (July 26, 1993);

I am grateful to the people. Interview with a correspondent of the newspaper "Rossiyski Fermer" (August 3, 1993);

"I promise you nothing": Interview with a correspondent of "Sobesednik" (August 10, 1993);

To His Excellency Mr. Jaime Paz Zamora, President of Bolivia (August 10, 1993);

To His Excellency Mr. Woo Kim Wie, President of the Republic of Singapore (August 10, 1993);

To His Excellency Mr. Rodrigo Borja Cevallos, President of Ecuador (August 10, 1993);

To His Excellency General Daniel Sassou Nguesso, President of the Republic of Congo (August 12, 1993);

Interview with the writer Alexander Prokhanov (August 12, 1993);

Opening remarks at a meeting with elected people's deputies from Bilasuvar, Jalilabad, Masalli, Lan-karan, Astara, Yardimli and Lerik districts and with executives and intellectuals from those districts; Closing remarks (August 13, 1993);

To the participants of the second international symposium "Energy, Ecology, Economy" (August 17, 1993);

Speech at a meeting with representatives of leading oil companies and corporations (August 17, 1993);

To His Excellency Mr. Al Haji Omar Bongo, President of the Republic of Gabon (August 17, 1993);

To His Excellency Mr. General Suharto, President of the Republic of Indonesia (August 17, 1993);

To the Chairman of the UN Security Council. Copy: UN Secretary-General (August 18, 1993);

Address to the people on the Azerbaijani National Television (August 23, 1993);

It is the duty of each of us to protect the statehood and territorial integrity of independent Azerbaijan (Speech at the All-Republican Meeting in Baku: August 24, 1993);

Interview with a correspondent of "Nezavisimaya Gazeta" (August 30, 1993);

Address to the participants of the International Conference on the Protection of War Victims (Geneva, August 30 - September 1, 1993) (August 31, 1993);

To Mr. Bill Clinton, President of the United States of America, Mr. Albert Gore, Vice President of the United States of America, Mr. Thomas Foley, Speaker of the United States of America Congress (September 2, 1993);

To Mr. Imamali Rakhmanov, Chairman of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Tajikistan (September 9, 1993);

Statement at a press conference by Heydar Aliyev, Chairman of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic, who exercises the powers of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan (September 10, 1993);

Composer Arif Malikova (September 14, 1993);

Speech at a meeting held at the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Azerbaijan (September 20, 1993);

Speech at a meeting with intellectuals at the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Azerbaijan (September 21, 1993);

Speech at a meeting with youth representatives at the Supreme Soviet of the Republic (September 22, 1993);

To Academician Azad Mirzajanzadeh (September 28, 1993);

Speech at a rally of representatives of industrial enterprises and labor collectives of the capital at the Baku Air Conditioning Plant (September 28, 1993);

Speech at a session of the Milli Majlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the discussion of the issue of whether there are illegal arrests in the republic (September 29, 1993);

Address on the occasion of the International "Day of the Elderly" (October 1, 1993);

To Mr. Jiao Shi, Chairman of the Standing Committee of the National People's Congress of China (October 1, 1993);

People's Poet Mammad Araza (October 6, 1993);

Speech at the inauguration ceremony of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan (October 10, 1993);

Congratulation to the people on the occasion of the Independence Day of Azerbaijan (October 18, 1993);

Speech at the meeting with the Chairman of the CSCE - the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Sweden, Margareta af Ugglas (October 26, 1993);

Statement at the joint press conference after the end of the negotiations with Margareta af Ugglas (October 26, 1993);

To the participants of the scientific and practical conference "The Republic of Turkey - 70" (October 26, 1993);

To the President of the Republic of Turkey, His Excellency Süleyman Demirel (October 28, 1993);

To the Prime Minister of the Republic of Turkey, Her Excellency Tansu Çiller (October 28, 1993);

To His Excellency Hüsameddin Çindoğu, Chairman of the Grand National Assembly of Turkey (October 28, 1993);

Statement at a joint press conference dedicated to the results of the negotiations between the Presidents of Azerbaijan and Iran (October 28, 1993);

Address to the people on National Television and Radio regarding the new attacks and aggression of the Armenian armed forces on the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan (November 2, 1993);

Speech at a meeting with former internationalist fighters (November 4, 1993);

Speech at a session of the Milli Majlis of the Republic of Azerbaijan (November 5, 1993);

Speech at a meeting with the leaders of political parties and public movements of Azerbaijan (November 17, 1993);

Speech at the republican meeting dedicated to the state of banking and financial, payment systems and import-export operations at the Presidential Palace and tasks in the field of their improvement (November 19, 1993);

Speech at the meeting dedicated to the socio-economic problems of the republic at the Presidential Palace (November 24, 1993);

Speech at the meeting dedicated to the elimination of serious shortcomings in the financial system and the supply of grain products to the population at the Presidential Palace (December 8, 1993);

Speeches during meetings in the frontline region - in Imishli, Fuzuli, Beylagan, Shamkir, Agjabedi districts and in the city of Ganja (December 11-12, 1993); Final speech at the meetings held in Agjabedi and Ganja regarding the situation in the frontline regions;

People's Artist Tahir Salahova (December 15, 1993);

Vice-President of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Academician Ziya Bunyadova (December 20, 1993);

Statement at a press conference in Paris during an official visit to France (December 21, 1993);

Statement at a meeting of the Council of Heads of State of the CIS (December 24, 1993);

To Academician Eldar Salayev (December 24, 1993);

Speech at a meeting with the family members of the National Heroes of Azerbaijan and martyrs for the freedom of our homeland (December 27, 1993);

New Year's address to the people (December 31, 1993);

Speech at a meeting with a group of young people who voluntarily left military units or evaded conscription, their parents and close relatives; Final speech (January 2, 1994);

To His Excellency John Major, Prime Minister of Great Britain (January 3, 1994);

Speech at a meeting with Colonel General Fyodor Reut, Commander of the Russian troops in Transcaucasia (January 6, 1994);

Congratulations to the Orthodox community in Azerbaijan on the occasion of the Nativity of the Prophet Jesus (January 7, 1994);

Azerbaijan is the homeland of Azerbaijanis living in all countries of the world: Speech at a meeting with a group of our compatriots living abroad (January 9, 1994);

The January 20 tragedy must be given a full political and legal assessment: Speech at a meeting of the State Commission for the preparation and holding of events related to the fourth anniversary of the January 20 tragedy (January 12, 1994);

The homeland needs your knowledge and experience: Speech at a meeting with a group of officers in the Presidential Administration (January 13, 1994);

Address to the people on the occasion of the fourth anniversary of the January 20 tragedy (January 19, 1994);

Tragedies that have occurred cannot break the will of our people: Speech at a meeting with the family members of those who were martyred during the tragic January events of 1990 in Baku and a group of those who were injured and disabled during those days (January 19, 1994);

We will liberate the homeland from the invaders: Speech at a meeting with soldiers and officers of the "N" military unit (January 24, 1994);

We have sufficient forces and capabilities to protect the sovereignty and territorial integrity of our country: Speech at a meeting with the Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation V. Kazimirov (January 31, 1994);

To the Minister of State for Foreign Affairs of the United Kingdom, Her Excellency Baroness Chalmers of Wolesi (February 4, 1994);

Speech at a meeting with the heads of the State Oil Company of the Republic of Azerbaijan, oil scientists and specialists (February 5, 1994);

To People's Artist, film director Tofiq Mehdi oglu Taghizade (February 7, 1994);

We would like you to become good specialists and serve our homeland, our people, our nation faithfully in the future: Speech at a meeting with Azerbaijani students who set off to study in Turkish universities (February 7, 1994);

To the participants of the Istanbul international "Peace and Patience" conference (February 7, 1994);

Interview with journalists at Bina airport while leaving for an official visit to the Republic of Turkey (February 8, 1994);

Speech at the official welcoming ceremony at the "Çankaya" pavilion, the residence of the President of the Republic of Turkey (February 8, 1994);

Heartfelt words written in the memorial book after visiting the tomb of the founder of the Republic of Turkey, prominent political and public figure Mustafa Kemal Atatürk at the "Anıtkabir" mausoleum in Ankara (February 8, 1994);

Speech at a banquet in honor of the President of Azerbaijan at the "Çankaya" pavilion in Ankara (February 8, 1994);

Speech at the Grand National Assembly of Turkey (February 9, 1994);

Speech at the signing ceremony of Turkish-Azerbaijani documents (February 9, 1994);

Speech at the presentation ceremony of the Honorary Doctorate of Ankara Hacettepe University (February 9, 1994);

Speech at a meeting with İhsan Doğramacı, Chairman of the Board of Directors of Bilkent University (February 9, 1994);

Speech at a meeting with ambassadors and members of diplomatic missions of world countries in Turkey in Ankara (February 9, 1994);

Speech before the delegates of the "Peace and Patience" international religious conference in Istanbul (February 10, 1994);

Speech at a meeting with a large group of Turkish businessmen (February 10, 1994);

Speech at a meeting with Azerbaijanis living in Turkey during an official visit (February 10, 1994);

Statement at a press conference for journalists and mass media representatives at the press center in Istanbul (February 11, 1994);

Opening remarks at a wide operational meeting at the Presidential Palace; Closing remarks (February 20, 1994);

Interview with journalists at Bina Airport before leaving for an official visit to Great Britain (February 22, 1994);

Speech at the Confederation of Industrialists of Great Britain (February 22, 1994);

Speech at the Royal Institute of International Affairs of Great Britain (February 23, 1994);

Speech at a meeting with Azerbaijanis living in Great Britain at the Hilton Hotel in London (February 23, 1994);

There are good prospects for the development of relations between Azerbaijan and Great Britain: Statement

at a press conference on the results of an official visit to Great Britain (February 24, 1994);

To the families of the victims of the Khojaly genocide (March 1, 1994);

To the staff of the Azerbaijan Telegraph Agency - AzerTAc (March 3, 1994);

Speech at a meeting dedicated to solving agricultural problems at the Presidential Palace (March 4, 1994);

Statement at a press conference in Beijing during an official visit to the People's Republic of China (March 8, 1994);

Speech at the Committee for the Assistance to the Development of International Trade in Beijing (March 9, 1994);

Speech at the Beijing Academy of Social Sciences (March 9, 1994);

Speech to journalists in Almaty on the results of the visit upon returning from the People's Republic of China to Baku (March 10, 1994);

Speech at a meeting with the President of Kazakhstan, Nursultan Nazarbayev, in Almaty (March 10, 1994);

Greetings to the people on the occasion of the holiday of fasting (March 12, 1994);

Visit to holy places on the day of the holiday of fasting (March 14, 1994);

Address to the people on the occasion of the holiday of Nowruz (March 20, 1994);

Closing speech at the meeting dedicated to the current situation in cotton growing and ways to solve problems related to the preparation for the sowing campaign at the Presidential Palace (March 30, 1994);

Meetings during a visit to the South-Western region of the Republic (April 9-10, 1994);

Address to the people on the republican national television and radio regarding the intensification of Armenia's aggression against Azerbaijan (April 12, 1994);

Statement at the meeting of the CIS Heads of State Council regarding the large-scale attacks of the Armenian armed forces on the territory of Azerbaijan (April 15, 1994);

Opening speech at the meeting dedicated to the tasks of mobilizing all forces to create a strong army in connection with the new attacks of the Armenian armed forces on the territory of Azerbaijan at the Presidential Palace; Closing speech (April 17, 1994);

Opening speech at the wide meeting of the senior officials of the Ministry of Internal Affairs at the Presidential Palace; Closing speech (April 29, 1994);

Congratulations to the Christian citizens of Azerbaijan on the occasion of Easter (April 29, 1994);

Statement to journalists at Bina airport before leaving for Brussels (May 3, 1994);

Speech at the NATO Council meeting in Brussels (May 4, 1994);

Speech at a press conference at the International Press Center in Brussels (May 4, 1994);

Statement at the signing ceremony of the "Partnership for Peace" framework document (May 4, 1994);

Meetings on the occasion of the 49th anniversary of the victorious end of the 1941-1945 war (May 9, 1994);

People's Artist of Azerbaijan Hajibaba Agarza oglu Baghirova (May 13, 1994);

Opening remarks at a meeting at the Presidential Palace dedicated to measures to strengthen social protection of the population and ensure stabilization of the financial situation of the economy; Final words (May 20, 1994);

Congratulations to the people on the occasion of the Eid al-Adha (May 20, 1994);

Meetings with Baku workers on the occasion of the Eid al-Adha (May 21, 1994);

Speech at the opening of the 1st International Exhibition on Oil and Gas Production in the Caspian Sea in Baku (May 24, 1994);

To People's Writer Ilyas Efendiyev (May 25, 1994).

For the first time in the bibliographic reference book, the complete collection of the Great Leader, that is, all 46 volumes, is given, both its description and composition are revealed. In general, the new book provides a bibliographic description of 1433 sources. Of these, 259 are his works, and 1174 are books published about him.

The fundamental bibliographic work also provides the awards of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev. The awards are reflected in several sections: For example, "Orders and medals of the USSR awarded to Heydar Aliyev", "Orders and medals received by the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev during the years of independence", "Honorary scientific titles awarded to the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev", "Honorary titles and prizes awarded to the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev".

Books reflecting Heydar Aliyev's commitment to education and science, demonstrating his care for science and education, are clear examples of our leader's service to the people.

The reforms carried out in the field of education and granting national status to the Azerbaijan Academy of Sciences, the autonomous status of a number of higher education institutions, including Baku State University, etc. are the results of Heydar Aliyev's successful policy on this path. The celebration of the anniversaries of personalities who played an important role in the life of the people in Azerbaijan, the cradle of culture, is a sign of Heydar Aliyev's high filial attitude to the national existence of our people, and this aspect is very clearly visible in the books included in the bibliography.

The value of the authoritative bibliographic reference book "About the National Leader Heydar Aliyev" in the third part, which contains bibliographic descriptions of 1433 sources, is further enhanced by the provision of eight subsections. These sections are: "Pages from the great life path of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev", "National Leader Heydar Aliyev is the architect of Azerbaijani statehood", "The stage of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev in the socio-economic development of Azerbaijan and the oil strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan", "Issues of the Azerbaijani language and literature in the heritage of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev", "National Leader Heydar Aliyev and the development of science, education, culture and art in Azerbaijan", "Great Leader Heydar Aliyev in fiction", "National Leader Heydar Aliyev and Azerbaijan in the international world", "Defended dissertations about the National Leader Heydar Aliyev", which play an important role in the moral and patriotic education of our youth and in the study of the heritage of Heydar Aliyev.

The bibliographic work was created with the aim of providing two auxiliary devices to facilitate its use. "This universal bibliographic work, prepared on the basis of the Action Plan for the "Year of Heydar Aliyev" of Baku State University, is a valuable source for studying and promoting the life and activities of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev, an example for everyone, and at the same time, for studying the rich heritage of the great leader" [6, p.11]

Novelty

The book also contains excerpts from Heydar Aliyev's world of thought, which is very useful for readers:

The state independence of Azerbaijan is our historical achievement!

The state independence of Azerbaijan is eternal, and irrevocable, the task before us is to protect and make it eternal.

The state independence of Azerbaijan is the most precious, most valuable achievement for us, and we will always protect this achievement - our state independence.

The people should not be for the state, but the state should be for the people.

Whoever stands in opposition, let him not stand in opposition to his Motherland, people, morality, profession.

Freedom of speech, freedom of thought, political pluralism should take a wide place in Azerbaijan, every citizen should feel free and independent.

If the people of any country understand their rights and can protect them, then even the smallest state will be as strong as the largest.

Freedom and independence are the national wealth of every nation.

Justice cannot be restored through injustice.

The more extensive presentation of the chronicle of the life and public activities of the Great Leader in the Soviet period, that is, before our independence, by referring to various archival sources, is the best contribution to researchers in obtaining the necessary information for that period. This area has been especially taken into account in the bibliographical work, and the chronicle of the life and activities of the president has been given in full. Undoubtedly, the bibliographical reference book is a very valuable and authoritative source of information in studying the heritage of the Great Leader, which users can benefit from. We hope that "Heydar Aliyev-100: Bibliographic reference book" will be a very valuable and important information tool in conveying the rich heritage of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev to future generations.

Conclusion

The bibliographic index fully reflects the genius of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev, the integrity of his personality, his high intellectual level, his deep scientific worldview, his unwavering loyalty to the ideas of national statehood, and his spiritual richness. At the same time, this bibliographic publication once again proves that very few prominent statesmen in the world can be compared with the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev in terms of the number and volume of their scientific and theoretical works. It is in this respect that the Na-

tional Leader Heydar Aliyev is a phenomenal personality, and the aforementioned bibliographic reference book is the most vivid example of this fact. "Heydar Aliyev-100: Bibliographic reference book", which is an invaluable source for scientists, researchers, teachers, students and a wide audience of readers working in various fields of science, will be made available to the use of our numerous intellectuals, especially the younger generation. I am confident that this necessary publication will soon be included in the funds of all republican libraries and made available to readers.

Undoubtedly, the bibliographic reference book is a very valuable and reliable source of information in studying the heritage of the Great Leader, which users can benefit from. We hope that "Heydar Aliyev-100: Bibliographic Reference Book" is a very valuable contribution to conveying the rich heritage of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev to future generations.

So far, a large number of scientific articles by the author have been published in prestigious, indexed journals published abroad (7-27).

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